

A SINGLE CUTANEOUS METASTASIS IN A MALE WITH BREAST CANCER TREATED WITH SURGERY AND ADJUVANT RADIOTHERAPY: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT Background: Breast cancer in men is a rare disease that represents <1% of cases. Currently, there is no consensus on the management of this disease in men, and even less in distant recurrences, the information that is available is extracted from the management in women and from retrospective studies. **Case report:** We present the case of a man with breast cancer stage IIA (T1, N1, M0) AJCC 2010 treated with modified radical mastectomy, adjuvant chemotherapy and radiotherapy, which during the follow-up presented a nodular lesion on the face with positive histopathologic report for a metastasis from a breast adenocarcinoma then he was treated aggressively with surgery and radiotherapy to the tumor bed with adequate local control and survival of the disease. **Conclusion:** Breast cancer in men represents <1% of the cases. There are a few reports of patients with a few metastatic lesions to the skin from breast cancer and most of these report mention that there is no consensus in the management of these patients given its low incidence and the treatment should be individualised according to each scenario.

KEYWORDS BREAST CANCER, CUTANEOUS METASTASIS, RADIOTHERAPY.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common cancers in the world is breast cancer, with a high incidence in all countries, with 1.7 million new cases in the world by 2012, representing the second highest incidence cancer and 25% of all cancers [1]. In the United States of America, breast cancer in men is a rare disease representing <1% of all breast cancers and <0.1% of cancer-related deaths in men, with an estimated by 2015 of 2350 American men living with this entity with 440 deaths related to it [2].

CASE REPORT

A 42-year-old man without significant medical history, who started his current illness On February 2014 with the presence of a tumour located in the left mammary region. On February 14, 2014, An excisional biopsy of the lesion was performed with a histological report of invasive carcinoma of the breast ducts, without a specific pattern, moderately differentiated, with a size of 1.3 x 1 cm, margins in contact with one of the tumour boundaries. On April 14, 2014, the patient underwent to a modified radical mastectomy, with a pathology report of a moderately differentiated metastatic adenocarcinoma to one of ten axillary lymph nodes resected, without evidence of residual tumor in the surgical bed, immunohistochemistry was positive for estrogens (++) in the 60%, negative progesterone, negative Her2, Ki67 in 10%, suggestive Luminal A subtype. Pathologic stage was IIA (T1, N1, M0) according to AJCC 2010. On May 17, 2014, after the surgery the patient received adjuvant chemotherapy doxorubicin plus paclitaxel at the end of chemotherapy the patient was treated with adjuvant radiotherapy with a dose of 50 Gy in 25 fractions concluding on March 05, 2015, subsequently On

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April 12, 2015, the patient started to take adjuvant hormone therapy with tamoxifen 20 mg orally every 24 hours. On January 23, 2017, During the surveillance, the patient presented to our department with a nodular lesion on the face of approximately 1 cm, near to the external epicanthic fold of the left eye, Figure 1 and 2. A biopsy was performed with a histological report of metastasis to the reticular and deep dermis from an adenocarcinoma moderately differentiated. Subsequently, on January 23, 2017, surgical resection was performed with pathology report: a residual malignant lesion with a tumor in one of the lateral limits. On March 31, 2017, the patient underwent to a margin re-excision with a report of residual metastasis of adenocarcinoma from the mammary duct with lower, with positive margins in deep surgical limit with the presence of malignant cells. On June 26, 2017, The immunohistochemistry showed positive estrogen receptors (++) in 80%, positive Ki67 in 5%. Consistent with a primary tumour of the breast. On April 26, 2017, a bone scan and chest-abdomen-pelvis CT were obtained both with negative results for metastasis disease. We discussed the patient's case in our clinical rounds, and we considered that the patient could get some benefited with adjuvant radiotherapy to the tumour bed on his face, considering the positive margins. From April 28, 2017, to Jun 1, 2017, we treated to the patient with adjuvant radiotherapy with electrons to the tumour bed adding 2 cm expansion to each side with a dose of 50 Gy in 25 fractions (image 3). The radiotherapy was given without any complication At 1-year follow-up, the patient is without clinical evidence of tumour activity at the primary site (chest wall) or the site of skin metastasis. Timeline of the patient's treatment Figure 1.

DISCUSSION

Breast cancer in men represents < 1% of cases, information available is from retrospective studies and extrapolated from studies in women[3]. The Risk factors in men are not known exactly, their relationship with testicular abnormalities such as undescended testicles, congenital inguinal hernia, orchiectomy, among others is not clear, between 3% and 7% of patients with Klinefelter syndrome can present it [4]. Regarding genetic alterations, a greater association with BRCA2 gene alteration has been observed up to 16%, associated with a younger presentation and worse prognostic[5]. Other related risk factors are the use of anti-androgenic drugs such as in the treatment of prostate cancer, Hodgkin's disease treated with radiotherapy and chronic hepatitis [5]. The diagnosis in these patients follows the guidelines of breast cancer in women, it is estimated that the average time of diagnosis delay compared to women is 10 months[6,7]. Breast cancer in men, expresses hormone receptors up to 90%, with a higher expression compared to breast cancer in women [6]. A higher prevalence of estrogen receptor than progesterone expression has been found in 90% and 81% respectively[6], finding the HER2 expression in at least the 15% of the cases. Androgen receptors are expressed in up to 95%, however, Its role is still uncertain [6]. The histopathological characteristics of invasive breast cancer in men show a similar distribution compared to women, up to 93.7% ductal, 2.6% papillary, 1.8% mucinous, and only 1.5% lobular[8]. 9% is diagnosed as in-situ carcinoma [9]. The main treatment in early stages is surgery[9], the most accepted modality in men is the modified radical mastectomy, with or without axillary lymph node dissection or sentinel lymph node biopsy, data from a study of 6263 men with breast cancer suggests that T1 tumors -T2, N0, M0 can undergo to breast-conserving surgery, however when using this modality

it is imperative the adjuvant radiotherapy[9]. The use of endocrine therapy is well accepted among men with breast cancer, tamoxifen has shown rates of improvement in overall survival among these patients[9]. The Recurrence on the skin, as in this patient, occurs more frequently in the locoregional site, so this distance presentation, is a sign of poor prognosis.[10] It presents as cellulitis and/or benign skin pathologies, the median survival in these patients with metastatic disease is 36 months[11]. The patient did not present other sites of identifiable active disease, radiotherapy provides better local control of the disease, and seems to have an effect on patient survival, being the patients who obtain the greatest benefit of the disease-free survival in whom present a complete clinical response to radiotherapy in metastasis[12].

CONCLUSION

The case presented is a man with early-stage breast cancer, treated according to international guidelines who developed a single skin metastasis on the face and treated aggressively with surgery and adjuvant radiotherapy with a high dose 50 Gy in 25 fractions with excellent disease control. Although some similar cases of this pathology with recurrence to the skin of the face have been described, there is not a clear consensus in the management. We believe that some of these patients may be managed with aggressive treatment and achieve long-term control of the disease.

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Conflict of Interest

At this moment, authors declared that through the process of this review was independent of conflict of interest that would lead to bias in this review.

References

1. Ghoncheh M, Pournamdar Z, Salehiniya H. Incidence and Mortality and Epidemiology of Breast Cancer in the World. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2016;17:43–6.
2. Ferzoco RM, Ruddy KJ. The Epidemiology of Male Breast Cancer. *Curr Oncol Rep*. 2016;18(1):1–6.
3. Giordano, A Review of the Diagnosis and Management of Male Breast Cancer, *The Oncologist* 2005;10:471–479.
4. Ali Jad Abdelwahab Yousef, Male Breast Cancer: Epidemiology and Risk Factors, *Seminars in Oncology* 44(2017)267–272, Elsevier.
5. Y.s. Hotko, male breast cancer: clinical presentation, diagnosis, treatment, *Exp Oncol* 2013 35, 4, 303–310
6. S.A.Massarweh, G.L.Choi, Special considerations in the evaluation and Management of breast cancer in men /*CurrProblCancer*40(2016)163–171
7. Culell P, Solernou L, Tarazona J et al. Male breast cancer: a multicentric study. *Breast J* 2007; 13
8. Giordano SH, Cohen DS, Buzdar AU et al. Breast carcinoma in men: a population-based study. *Cancer* 2004;101:51–57.
9. K. J. Ruddy* & E. P. Winer, Male breast cancer: risk factors, biology, diagnosis, treatment, and survivorship, *Annals of oncology*, 24: 1434-1443, 2013.

10. R. Foerster, Metastatic Male Breast Cancer: A Retrospective Cohort Analysis, *Breast Care* 2014;9:267–271 (8)
11. B. kalmykow, cutaneous metastases in breast cancer, February 2011. Volume 15, Number 1, *Clinical Journal of Oncology*
12. F. Jafre, prognosis, for isolated skin recurrence after breast cancer treated by mastectomy, *anticancer research* 29: 1697-1702 (2009).